

The Impact of Social Media on Intellectual Security at Students of Universities: An Applied Study on Jordanian Universities

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Abstract

Social media has been prevalently used, especially among students in Universities, leading to harmful behaviours in educational institutions. The current study has been focused on revealing the levels of social media use and intellectual security at students in Jordanian Universities, and investigating the impact of social media use on intellectual security. A descriptive approach was used to achieve the study aim and its related objectives. A self-reported questionnaire was used for collecting data from the study sample that consisted of (250) students who were selected randomly. The study has found that the use of social media and intellectual security in the study sample was found at a high level with the mean of (4.15 ± 0.34) and (4.18 ± 0.72) respectively. Also, the results revealed a significant and negative impact of social media use on the students' intellectual security with $(F = -357.106, P = 0.00 < 0.05)$.

Introduction

The great information revolution in communication and information technology played a prominent role in attracting different society age groups, especially the youth. Particularly, Social media networks, such as (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc.) have become one of the most important factors and catalysts for intellectual, political, social, and psychological changes (Seo et al., 2014; Sampasa-Kanyinga and Lewis, 2015). In addition, they have effectively contributed to the dissemination of information and the speed of its access to the largest possible number of users. The traditional means of the world have put the citizen in the place of the consumer and the simple recipient. Appositively, the Internet has transformed the receiver into a sender through interactive capabilities (Raza et al., 2020; Bongiovanni et al., 2020).

Ease and speed of obtaining information through social media, in addition to the diversity of formation obtained, has resulted in many positive aspects that are not easy to enumerate; Using social media has led to an increase in knowledge gaining and sharing in different fields of life (social, economic, political, intellectual, etc.), strengthened communication and cooperation between individuals as well as groups at the national and international levels, accelerated achievement of work-related tasks, and reduced the financial costs, effort, and time required to achieve practical and educational tasks (Reid and Weigle, 2014; Wickramanayake, 2021).

In contrast, misuse or overuse of social media has resulted in many negative aspects that bring risks to the individual and society as a whole. Its misuse has resulted in some psychological and physical problems for children, and increased isolation among some young people (Vandoninck et al., 2012; Veil, Buehner, and Palenchar, 2011). In this context, Alabdulkareem, (2015) confirmed that the excessive use of social media has led to the dismissal of young people from practicing beneficial work, and failure to complete some official and educational work tasks. Social media often lead to the rapid spread of rumors that may stir conflict and strife in society and among its sects causing disintegration of the societal tissue and destabilizing the security and stability of the home as a whole (Griffiths and Kuss, 2017).

Hence, there is a persistent need to study social media networks and their impact on intellectual security in society, especially on university students, as intellectual security is associated with national security that achieves stability at the home and preserves its unity, beliefs, and culture. This positive result of intellectual security brings about interdependence and social communication between groups of society, sects, and individuals. On the other hand, using social media improperly or excessively may create negative outcomes that harm societies. Therefore, this study comes to identify the impact of social media networks on the intellectual security of university students, as one of the society segments that most use social media, and therefore the most vulnerable to its positive and negative aspects.

Research problem

The number of social media users among university students in Jordan has been increasing (Saadeh, Saadeh, and De La Torre, 2020). This may be attributed to that social media has provided a virtual environment for young

people to exchange ideas and information, discuss common concerns such as living and hot societal issues, declare their opinions and perspectives impartially and freely on global and local political issues. Also, social media has helped people share their personal lives with others. Particularly, social media has provided many benefits among university youth, such as cooperative learning among students in groups, and the exchange of educational information and videos, which increased the efficiency of the university learning process (Habes et al., 2020). However, social media has also led to the emergence of some negative effects in Jordanian universities, such as University violence, school dropout, and other impacts on the intellectual security of the university community (Alshamaila, 2018; Al-Shdayfat, 2018). Thus, the study problem is represented in the following question:

Is there a significant impact of using social media on intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities?

From this main question, the following questions can be branched:

1. What are the most used social media types by students of Jordanian universities?
2. What is the level of use of social media at students of Jordanian universities?
3. What is the level of intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities?
4. Is there a significant impact of using social media on intellectual security (social and psychological, political, economic, and ethical) at students of Jordanian universities?

Aim & Objectives

The study aims to investigate the impact of using social media on intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities.

From the study aim the following objectives can be branched:

1. To identify the most used social media types by students of Jordanian universities.
2. To identify the level of use of social media at students of Jordanian universities.
3. To identify the level of intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities.
4. To investigate the impact of social media use on intellectual security (social and psychological, political, economic, and ethical) at students of Jordanian universities.

Research significance

From the theoretical perspective, the current study should contribute to increasing awareness of university students of the negative consequences resulting from the excessive and wrongful use of social media in all its types. Also, researchers interested in this field may find an opportunity to further investigate other problems caused by social media depending on the background results of the current study.

From the practical perspective, students in Jordanian universities may get some alternative solutions, based on the study results and its discussion, to be far away from the negative effects of their excessive and abuse of social media in all its types.

Research hypothesis

According to the research questions, it can be hypothesized that:

H0-1: There is not a significant impact of social media on intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From this main hypothesis, the following sub-hypotheses can be formulated:

1. H0-1-1: There is not a significant impact of using social media on social and psychological intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).
2. H0-1-2: There is not a significant impact of using social media on ethical intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).
3. H0-1-3: There is not a significant impact of using social media on economic intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).
4. H0-1-4: There is not a significant impact of using social media on political intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Theoretical Background

Use of Social Media

Several studies have been conducted on social media and its impact on human life. Social media affects human life, positively or negatively, through its dimensions. The dimensions of social media represent the different facets of their uses by people to meet their various requirements.

Social communications

Generally, Social media is widely used by people to meet their social relationships and requirements. It is known that most people today resort to social media to urge their daily social issues, such as e-discussion among

the family members, relatives, or among members of the same tribe (Gashami, Libaque-Saenz, and Chang, 2020). Also, university students use social networks to discuss some relational issues rather than educational aspects, such as mutual houses' visits, groups' tours, or some social activities that they practiced together in their university (Dzogbenuku, Amoako, and Kumi, 2020; Wickramanayake, 2021).

Students' learning

Students can use social media to practice their learning activities. They can use some social media applications to share information about their courses' activities, make scientific problems' solutions, discuss their lectures' contents, and keep their lectures' attendance (Weerasundera, 2014; Wickramanayake, 2021).

Online learning via social media helps students practice their learning activities in urgent situations (Siddiqui and Singh, 2016; Raza et al., 2020). For instance, university students have been sharing their information on social media during CORONA disease (COVID-19). In this risky health situation, social media applications have allowed students to be in contact with their instructors not less than in face-to-face education. Moreover, online learning through social media applications provides another important merit by allowing students to get their learning anytime and anyplace.

Games and entertainment

The continuous and unlimited development of information technology and internet applications helped social media to get unprecedented pace to all science fields' progress (i.e.: economic, social, health, business, etc.). Social media is equipped with highly developed applications that allow users to practice an open world of games and entertainment (Raza et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2010). Games and Entertainment programs are described by flexibility; they are designed so that each game and entertainment application can fit a certain age of youth (Zhang et al., 2010). Although university students need to play some games using social media, but the abuse of this type of technology may lead to many negative effects on the students and their relatives.

Culture and awareness

Undoubtedly, social media reinforced principles of the world cultures and helped people throughout different countries to exchange their cultural events. In this context, people have gained new norms and customs that have changed their thinking and behaviour to be better. Such cultural exchange throughout different countries has reinforced rapprochement between cultures (León-Salas & Quesada, 2020).

Nevertheless, youth may be affected negatively by the cultural exchange on social media. Such negative effect reflects on the change of people's beliefs, thoughts, and behaviour (Wijesundara, 2014). University students are considered as the most exposed to the cultural exchange via social media. University students try to build new relationships with others from a different culture, read some different events or may watch some videos from a different culture. Gaining contradictory events to the original culture may lead to break up cultural tissue in the society and create strange and harmful behaviour by the youth community (Abu-Snieneh et al., 2019).

Intellectual Security

Using social media to meet different people's needs may support intellectual security, or interrupt it if they are used improperly. The literature of intellectual security studied intellectual security from different dimensions.

Social and psychological intellectual security

Intellectual security plays a major role in achieving social and psychological stability for people enhancing their positive participation and contribution in development and prosperity in different civil society institutions. Today, the interaction with the Internet may lead to sabotage social ties because it changes the nature of human relations by encouraging them to contact without face-to-face interaction (Seo et al., 2014). It was confirmed that social and psychological problems resulting from the use of the social network are many; some of them are related to the relationship of the individual with the family, and the others are related to the relationship of the individuals with their community, such as concealment of personality, addiction, and social isolation (Al-Khataibeh, 2017).

Ethical intellectual security

Using the social networks has led to the reduction of the restrictions and limits used to control informational behavior, and it became possible for some people to bypass values, standards, and social control (Sampasa-Kanyinga and Lewis, 2015). However, some technological solutions have been provided to prevent the finding of these sites (filtering), but many internet surfers can access them.

Ethical intellectual security is concerned, in the first place, with protecting the belief and thinking of the youth and immunizing them from misleading suspicions and doubts about their constants. That ethical intellectual security derives its roots from the nation's belief and its universals, defines its identity, realizes itself, and takes into account its characteristics (Griffiths and Kuss, 2017). Social media in its various types may cause

imbalance for the doctrinal and legal constants, blurring of the intellectual and legal reference, dogmatic wars, attack on the sacred constants, and make youth exposed to extremist ideas (Gad and Ahmad, 2019).

Economic intellectual security

While social networks may help change the ways of economic performance by lowering prices and wages, in addition to enabling people to do their work while they are at home, the abuse of them may cause some economic problems, including financial crimes such as gambling, money laundering, crimes of burglary over credit card numbers, falsifying data and destroying websites, causing economic blows to owners of major factories, international companies and banks (Zein El-Abdein and Nor-Eldein, 2019).

Political intellectual security

Intellectual security realizes political stability for young people by reinforcing commitment and loyalty to the political leadership, achieves interdependence, solidarity, and cooperation among people. Moreover, Intellectual security provides safety of thought, resistance to ideas that are foreign to society, which enhances the stability of internal conditions of the country, and preserves its material and moral capabilities (Al-Smadi, 2016; Veil, Buehner, and Palenchar, 2011).

Although social media has played a major role in managing political issues and enhancing cooperation, coordination, and integration of its dimensions, it has led to many political problems because of its misuse, whether intentionally or unintentionally. For instance, two main political issues can be discussed here, which are hostile sites, and electronic espionage (Al-Khataibeh, 2017; Ahmad, 2019):

Hostile sites: hostile sites are widely spread on the Internet. Some of these sites are directed against the policy of a state, or a certain belief or sect, or even against someone occupying a prestigious site. Generally, hostile sites aim in the first place to distort the image of the state, belief, or person.

Electronic espionage: In the current era that is described as the information age, and due to the presence of highly advanced technologies the borders of the state are permissible by spy satellites and satellite broadcasting. The means of espionage have shifted from traditional methods to modern methods in which information technology is used widely.

Literature Review

A study conducted by Zein El-Abdein and Nor-Eldein (2019) aimed to determine the role of social networks in improving intellectual security from the viewpoint of Umm Alqura university students at their Bachelor's degree. The study used a descriptive approach, and the study sample consisted of (360) students who were selected randomly. The study results revealed that university students use social networks mostly for entertainment and the exchange of views.

Another study conducted by Al-Khataibeh (2017) to investigate the relationship between social media and intellectual security among undergraduates-university students from two Jordanian universities; Jordan University and Balqa university. A descriptive approach was used to achieve the study objectives, and a self-administered questionnaire was used as the instrument tool for data collection from the study sample. The study sample was composed of (135) students selected conveniently. The study results showed that social media plays a significant role in spreading extremist discourses (political, social, and religious).

Also, Ahmad (2019) investigated the relationship between the use of social networking sites and the intellectual security among the students of social work. The study used a descriptive approach. The study sample was composed of (145) students who were selected conveniently. It was found by the results that there was no significant difference among the mean scores of respondents about their intellectual security due to their gender and living place.

Al-Khaza'leha (2019) applied a study on university students to identify the awareness level gained through online dialogue on social media interaction. The study used the descriptive approach by using a self-administered questionnaire that was designed for data collection from (494) students from Al-Ain University, who were randomly selected as the study sample. The study findings confirmed that the awareness level is high. Also, the findings confirmed that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of respondents about the awareness due to the gender.

It can be noted from the previous studies that they aimed to investigate the effect of using social media on intellectual security, and the results confirmed that there is a negative impact of using social media on intellectual security. The current study depended on the previous studies above in building its theoretical background, research design, methodology, and analysis approach. The current study is differentiated from the previous studies in its focus on the negative effect side of social media on intellectual security and in its application environment, where it has been applied in the Jordanian educational environment.

Methodology

Research approach

Descriptive analytical approach was used as a suitable approach for meeting the research aim and objectives.

The Study Population And Sample

The study population consisted of all students in Jordanian universities from different university stages and different scientific options. The study sample consisted of (250) students who were selected randomly from the study population. Table (1) shows the descriptive statistics of the study sample.

Table (1). Descriptive statistics of the study sample

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Male	100	40
Female	150	60
Total	250	100.0
Facebook	70	28
Twitter	63	25
Whatsapp	50	20
Instagram	37	15
Others	30	12
Total	250	100.0

Table (1) shows that (60%) of the sample is female, whereas (40%) is male. This indicates that females are more inclined to use social media to practice their social communication with others (such as friends or family members). Also, most of the study sample (28%) is Facebook users as the most used social medium. This affirms that most of the students in Jordanian universities use Facebook as the most effective and fast social medium for communication with others, and as means to follow the at –the- moment news in its different categories (i.e.: political, social, cultural, economic, etc.). Additionally, the students use Facebook as an effective social medium to practice online learning, especially in the current health situation, where the unprecedented disease, COVID-19, has spread worldwide.

Study instrument

A self-administered questionnaire was used for collecting data from the study sample. The study instrument included two main sections; the first section included the descriptive questions about the gender of the student and their most used social medium. The second section of the study instrument included questions about the measurement scale of the study variables. 5- A likert-scale was used for measuring the level of social media use by the students in Jordanian universities. The measurement scale ranged from (1= strongly disagree) to (5= strongly agree).

Likert scale has been processed according to the following equation (Sekaran and Bougie, 2012):

$$\text{Class Length} = (\text{Upper Limit} - \text{lower limit}) / (\text{The number of levels})$$

$$\text{Class length} = (5-1)/3 = 1.33$$

This means that:

$1.33 + 1 = 2.33$, so the first degree of respondents agreement is (1 to 2.33) expressing the low level.

$2.33 + 1.33 = 3.66$, so the second degree of respondents agreement is (2.34 to 3.67) expressing the medium level.

$3.67+1.33 = 5$, so the third degree of respondents agreement is (3.68 to 5) expressing the high level.

Based on the previous equation, the relative agreement was determined; Low agreement score includes the group of items with a mean of $< (2.34)$, Medium agreement score includes the group of items with a mean of (2.34 to 3.67), and The high agreement score degree of approval includes items with mean of (>3.68).

The questionnaire comprised of 42 items; two items for the describing the demographic variables of the study sample, and 40 items for measuring the study variables.

The instrument validity and reliability

Content Validity

To verify the validity of the study tool, it was presented to (10) experienced and specialized arbitrators. After some adjustments made, the general agreement between the arbitrators reached (90%) regarding the extent to which the tool achieved the research objectives, questions and hypotheses.

Construct Validity

To verify the construct validity of the study variables, correlation coefficients between the variables of each scale were calculated, as well as between each variable with its scale (Table 2).

Table (2) . Correlation coefficients between the variables of “Social Media” scale

		1	2	3	4	(Total)
Social communications	Pearson Correlation	1				
Students' learning	Pearson Correlation	0.66**	1			
Games and entertainment	Pearson Correlation	0.53*	0.759**	1		
Culture and awareness	Pearson Correlation	0.55*	.0451**	.575**	1	
Social Media (Total)	Pearson Correlation	.781**	.802**	.857**	.778**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

It can be noted from Table (2) that the values of correlation coefficients between variables of the “social media” scale ranged between (0.451- 0.759) and statistically significant at ($\alpha = 0.01$), which confirms the consistency between all variables of “social media” scale. Also, the values of correlation coefficients between (social media variables) and social media as a whole ranged between (0.778- 0.857) and statistically significant at ($\alpha = 0.01$). This result indicates that all social media variables are appropriate to measure social media use.

Table (3) . Correlation Coefficients between the variables of intellectual security

		1	2	3	4	Total
Social and psychological intellectual security	Pearson Correlation	1				
Political intellectual security	Pearson Correlation	.684**	1			
Economic intellectual security	Pearson Correlation	.619**	.608**	1		
Ethical intellectual security	Pearson Correlation	.541**	.661**	.549**	1	
Intellectual Security (Total)	Pearson Correlation	.848**	.765**	.801**	.824**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

It can be noted from Table (3) that the values of correlation coefficients between the variables of the “intellectual security” scale ranged between (0.541- 0.684) and statistically significant at ($\alpha = 0.01$), which confirms the consistency between all variables of “intellectual security” scale. Also, the values of correlation coefficients between (intellectual security variables) and “intellectual security “as a whole ranged between (0.765- 0.848) and statistically significant at ($\alpha = 0.01$). This result indicates that all “intellectual security “variables are appropriate to measure” intellectual security”.

Reliability

The reliability of the study instrument was verified using Cronbach alpha coefficient, that should be (≤ 0.60) (Haire, 2011). (Table 4).

Table (4) shows that Cronbach Alpha for “Social Media” dimensions ranged between (0.83- 0.86) and the total Cronbach Alpha for “Social Media” value is (0.87), which confirms that “Social Media” scale can be described by reliability and all data collected for measuring “Social Media” are reliable to measure all dimensions of “Social Media Use”.

Table (4).Cronbach’s alpha coefficients of the study variables

Number	Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	Number	variable	Cronbach’s Alpha
1	Social communications	0.86	1	Social and psychological intellectual security	.910
2	Students’ learning	0.83	2	Ethical intellectual security	.909
3	Games and entertainment	0.85	3	Economic intellectual security	.898
4	Culture and awareness	0.83	4	Political intellectual security	.910
			5		
Social media (Total)		0.87	Intellectual security (Total)		0.91

Also, Table (4) shows that Cronbach Alpha for “intellectual security” dimensions ranged between (0.89- 0.91) and the total Cronbach Alpha for “intellectual security” value is (0.91), which confirms that “Intellectual Security” scale can be described by reliability and all data collected for measuring “Intellectual Security” are reliable to measure all dimensions of “intellectual security”.

All the tests done for the instrument validity and reliability confirms that the instrument is valid and reliable to measure the levels of each variable and test the study hypotheses.

Results

The study results have been focused on answering the main question of the study, which is:

Is there a significant impact of using social media on intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities?

This question can be answered by providing results of all its sub-questions, as follows:

Question (1)

What are the most used social media types by students of Jordanian universities?

It can be noticed from table (5) that, Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp are the most used social media by university students in Jordan with means of (4.84, 4.58, and 4.41) respectively, whereas LinkedIn, Tumblr, and Flickr are the least used ones with means of (2.81, 2.65, and 2.34) respectively.

Table (5).Means and standard deviations of social media levels use by the study sample.

Type of social media	Mean±SD
Facebook	4.84± 0.34
Twitter	4.58± 0.52
WhatsApp	4.41±0.63
You tube	4.23±0.72
Instagram	3.65±0.74
Snapchat	3.45±0.79
Linkedin	2.81±1.24
Tumblr	2.65±1.36
FLickr	2.34±1.38

Question (2)

What is the level of use of social media at students of Jordanian universities?

It can be noted from the table (6) that the universities' students in Jordan use social media at a high level with a mean of (4.15), and a standard deviation of (0.34). Also, they use social media mostly to practice their social communication in the first order with a mean of (4.81), second to practice their learning process with a mean of (4.30), third to play games and other entertainment programs, and finally to increase their culture and awareness.

Table (6). Means and standard deviations of social media usage categories

Number	Social media usage category	Mean±SD
1	Social communications	4.81±0.67
2	Students' learning	4.30±0.44
3	Games and entertainment	3.76±0.57
4	Culture and awareness	3.74±0.68
Total		4.15±0.34

Question (3)

What is the level of intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities?

It can be noticed from table (7) that intellectual security at the universities' students in Jordan is high with a mean of (4.18), and a standard deviation of (0.72). Also, it can be noted from the table that social intellectual security and ethical intellectual security have occupied the highest order with a mean of (4.94), (4.88), and standard deviation of (0.42) and (0.52) respectively. Economic intellectual security and political intellectual security have occupied the medium order with mean of (3.65), (3.26) and standard deviations (0.85), (0.87) respectively.

Table (7). Means and standard deviations of intellectual security categories

Num.	Intellectual Security Dimensions	Mean± SD
1	Social and psychological intellectual security	4.94±0.42
2	Ethical intellectual security	4.88±0.52
3	Economic intellectual security	3.65±0.85
4	Political intellectual security	3.26±0.87
Total		4.18±0.72

Question (4)

Is there a significant impact of using social media on intellectual security (social and psychological, political, economic, and ethical) at students of Jordanian universities?

This question can be responded testing the main hypothesis and its sub-hypotheses:

First: Testing the main hypothesis

H0-1: there is not a significant impact of using social media on intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Multiple regression analysis was used for testing the impact of social media on the intellectual security. The results were shown in Table No. (8) and Table (9).

Table (8). Results of "Social Media" impact on "Intellectual Security"

Model Summary		ANOVA			
Model	R	R Square	df	F	Sig.
1	-.928 ^a	.860	5/250	-357.106	0.000

Predictors: (Constant), Social communications, Students' learning, Games and entertainment, Culture and awareness.

The table (8) indicates that there is a statistically significant impact of social media on intellectual security, where the value of F (-357.106) is significant at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and represents the significance of this model at the degree of freedom (250/5). The value of R^2 (0.860) indicates that the main dimension (Social Media) explains (86.0%) of the variance related to intellectual security at the university students' sector in Jordan. The value of R (-0.928) indicates the strong relationship between "Social Media" And "Intellectual Security".

Based on this result, we can reject the main null hypothesis above, and replace it with the alternative hypothesis stating that:

Ha-1: There is a significant impact of Social Media on Intellectual Security at Jordanian universities' students at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Table (9). Coefficients of Social Media (IV) and Intellectual Security (DV)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.399	.156		-2.565	.012
	Social communications	-.167	.054	-.707	-3.500	.002
	Students' learning	-.716	.044	-.811	-6.293	.000
	Games and entertainment	-.550	.236	-.154	-2.336	.034
	Culture and awareness	-.810	.260	-.419	-3.101	.007

Dependent Variable: Intellectual Security

The results of the coefficients in table (9) indicate that among all social media dimensions, students' learning has the greatest impact on intellectual security with a *Beta* coefficient (-0.811), and the p-value is ($0.00 < 0.05$). Also, what reinforces this result is the value of (T) which was calculated as (-6.293). Dimension of (Social communications) has occupied the second rank in its impact on intellectual security with ($\beta = -0.707$, $p = 0.002 < 0.05$), and reinforced by the value of (T = -3.500). Dimension of (Culture and awareness) occupied the third rank in its impact on intellectual security with ($\beta = -0.419$, $p = 0.007 < 0.05$), and reinforced by the value of (T = -3.101). Finally, dimension (Games and entertainment) has occupied the fourth rank in its impact on intellectual security with ($\beta = -0.154$, $p = 0.034 < 0.05$), and reinforced by the value of (T= -2.33).

Based on this result, it can be concluded that social media in all its dimensions have a significant impact intellectual security at the significant level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) “.

Second: Testing the Sub-Hypotheses

a) Testing the First Sub-Hypothesis (H0-1)

H0-1-1: There is not a significant impact of using social media on social intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Table (10). Result of “Social Media” Impact on social intellectual security.

Model		Model Summary		Coefficients.		
		R	R ²	Std. Error	t	Sig
1	(Constant)	-.730 ^a	.533	.279	2.446	.016
	social media			.068	-11.601	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Social and psychological Intellectual Security

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media

Table (10) indicates that there is a statistically significant impact of (Social Media) on social intellectual security, where the value of T (-11.601) is significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The value of R^2 (0.53) indicates that (Social Media) explains (53.3%) of the variance related to (Social Intellectual Security). The correlation coefficient (R) (-73.0%) indicates a strong relationship between (Social Media) and “Social Intellectual Security”. Based on this result, we reject the null hypothesis (H0-1) and accept the alternative hypothesis (Ha-1) which states that:

Ha-1-1: There is a significant impact of using social media on social intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

b) Testing the Second Sub-Hypothesis (H0-2):

H0-1-2: There is not a significant impact of using social media on ethical intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Table (11). Result of “social media” impact on Ethical Intellectual Security.

Model		Model Summary		Coefficients.		
		R	R ²	Std. Error	t	Sig
1	(Constant)	-.792 ^a	.627	.126	5.527	.000
	Social media			.032	-25.617	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Ethical Intellectual Security

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social media.

Table (11) indicates that there is a statistically significant impact of (Social Media) on (Ethical Intellectual Security), where the value of T (25.61) is significant at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The value of R^2 (0.627) indicates that (Social Media) explains (62.7%) of the variance related to (Ethical Intellectual Security). The correlation coefficient (R = -79.2%) indicates a strong relationship between (social media) and ethical intellectual security.

Based on this result, we reject the null hypothesis (H0-2), and accept the alternative hypothesis (Ha-2) which states that:

Ha-1-2: There is a significant impact of using social media on ethical intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

c) Testing the Third Sub-Hypothesis (H0-3):

H0-3: There is not a significant impact of using social media on economic intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Table (12).Result of Social Media on Economic Intellectual Security.

Model		Model Summary		Coefficients.		
		R	R ²	Std. Error	t	Sig
1	(Constant)	-.675 ^a	.456	.773	1.230	.234
	Social Media			.194	-3.991	.001

a. Dependent Variable: economic intellectual security.

b. Predictors: (Constant), social media

Table (12) indicates that there is a statistically significant impact of (Social Media) on (Economic Intellectual Security), where the value of T (-3.99) is significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The value of R^2 (0.456) indicates that (Social Media) explains (45.6%) of the variance related to (Economic Intellectual Security). The correlation coefficient (R) (-67.5%) indicates a strong relationship between (Social Media) and Economic Intellectual Security. Based on this result, we reject the null hypothesis (H0-3) and accept the alternative hypothesis (Ha-3) which states that:

Ha-1-3: There is a significant impact of using social media on economic intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

d) Testing the Fourth Sub-Hypothesis (H0-4):

H0-1-4: There is not a significant impact of using social media on political intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Table (13). Result of (Stress and Conflict Management) impact on TWP

Model		Model Summary		Coefficients.		
		R	R ²	Std. Error	t	Sig
1	(Constant)	-.714 ^a	.510	.842	.339	.738
	Social media			.212	-4.447	.000

a. Dependent Variable: political intellectual security

b. Predictors: (Constant), social media

Table (13) indicates that there is a statistically significant impact of (Social Media) on (Political Intellectual Security), where the value of T (-4.44) is significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The value of R² (0.510) indicates that (Social Media) explains (51.0%) of the variance related to (Political Intellectual Security). The correlation coefficient (R) is (71.4%), which indicates a strong relationship between (Social Media) and Political Intellectual Security. Based on this result, we reject the null hypothesis (H0-4) and accept the alternative hypothesis (Ha-4) which states that:

Ha-1-4: There is a significant impact of using social media on political intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Discussion

Discussion of social media and intellectual security levels at students of Jordanian universities

It can be revealed that social intellectual security has the highest degree of the respondents' acceptance. This indicates that university students in Jordan use social media mostly for practicing social activities, and thus see that social intellectual security is the most affected by social media abuse. It can be inferred that when social media is used properly, the negative effect of social media will be reduced on Social intellectual security.

Ethical intellectual security was found in the second rank according to the students' responses. This indicates that university students affect their ethical behaviour negatively as Jordanian society is characterized as a conservative society, and thus students evaluate some activities on social media may be as penetrative to their social norms and habits.

Political and economic dimensions of intellectual security were evaluated in the medium degree of acceptance. This confirms that university students see that social media cause them to be in an insecure manner because of some rumors and incorrect economic and political news, especially their country witnesses some economic and political challenges.

Discussion of the social media impact on intellectual security at students of Jordanian universities:

From the social perspective

With the development of social media applications as well as the revolution of cultural communications, social media is no longer just a communication network, but one of the basic elements in the social tissue. It may tighten up or break up the social relationships in society. Interaction with social media applications may sabotage social ties because it changes the nature of human relations.

Sampasa-Kanyinga and Lewis (2015) explained how social media makes people vulnerable to possible distortions and deviations in their lifestyles. They asserted that individuals may be exposed to be victims of social media when they practice their activities that may reflect negatively on their lifestyle. In this manner, the abuse of social media may create indignation on the universities' students so that they may be victims of following malicious and distorted opinions, forming a public opinion towards a particular issue regardless of its validity, be exposed to sabotage vital systems, believing rumors and misconceptions that may harm the individual and society, deal with facilitating operations of money laundering across state borders.

Social media has contributed to the emergence of the phenomenon of psychological and social alienation among some university students by their wish to live outside their current society (Vandoninck et al., 2012). Additionally, most of the social problems affecting students in their universities, such as concealment of personality, addiction, social isolation, some family problems, and emotional dryness, are created as the result of excessive use of social media.

From the economic perspective

although social networks help change the ways of economic performance in terms of low prices and wages, in addition to the ability of people to perform their work while they are at home, the abuse of social network is associated with some economic problems including financial crimes, gambling, money laundering, theft of credit card numbers, falsification of data, and the destruction of sites, which may cause economic strikes to the owners of major factories, international companies, banks, and ministries.

From the ethical perspective

Despite that social media provide an effective way to educate young people and fight intrusive thoughts, but on the other hand, it may lead to negative effects. Using social media lead youth to exceed restrictions of social values, norms, and controls, such as the spread of pornographic sites that destroy some values and ethics, disseminate vice, distract youth from their religion, customs and traditions, and push them to commit crimes and practice forbidden actions (Weerasundera, 2014).

Social media has contributed to violating the privacy of others through electronic espionage operations. The study sample believed that social media contributed to the spread of the phenomenon of impersonation, which affected the recipient's lack of confidence in everything written on various social media. Also, social media have contributed to publishing pornographic videos and image clips, and pictures that are immoral and contrary to the teachings of Islam, and dismantling family and social ties. The value system of university students has fluctuated as a result of cultural intervention. Moreover, the excessive use of communication via social media has led to addiction use of social media and time to be wasted.

From the political perspective

Many countries assist their citizens to use social media to clarify the country's positions about a specific issue to facilitate access to information as quickly as possible. On the other hand, many organizations and internationally banned groups use it to spread rumors and incite public opinion against rulers and political leaders to divide the society's unity and strike its tissue and capabilities.

Although social media has a major role in strengthening countries' leadership and their authorities, support democracy, and freedom of expression, it may lead to negative political implications (Dzogbenuku et al., 2020). Students in Jordanian universities are exposed to hostile sites that are widely spread on social media. Some of these sites are directed against a state's policy, a certain belief or sect, or even against a person.

Cyber espionage is another challenge facing university students on social media. In the information age, due to the presence of highly advanced technologies; the borders of the state have been violated by spy satellites and satellite broadcasting. The means of espionage have shifted from traditional methods to advanced ones in which more developed technology is used and may penetrate more personally private information

Abuse of social media by university students leads them to be a part of political crises. In this context, social media may create an opportunity for polarization operations from suspicious networks, increase tension, and deepen the disagreement and strife between governments and citizens.

Conclusion

Social networks are considered one of the most popularly created elements of the information technology and communication revolution that the world witnessed today. Their sound prevalence has put people in an inevitable situation to use them as an essential and attractive technology that can meet all human life purposes (social, economic, political, cultural, educational, etc.). However, social networks may not positively serve their users; when used excessively or wrongfully; social networks may lead their users to be victims to personal, group, or even societal dilemmas. Accordingly, this is motivating us persistently and diligently to legalize the use of social networks to protect our life against its use's risks. This study has been focused to clarify this opposite side of social networks through their negative impact on society, represented by the students of Jordanian universities. The study has proved that the excessive and wrongful use of social networks leads to a negative impact on intellectual security in all its dimensions (social, ethical, economic, and political). This pushes us forward to repeat our thinking in how to justify and reorient our behaviour and our students' behaviour in their universities how to use properly various social networks for serving our society safely and effectively. This interactive and recommended behaviour of (i.e. students' protection against excessive use of social media) is very important as our universities have been witnessing youth violence.

Recommendations

According to the study results and discussion, the following recommendations can be provided:

1. Universities have to adopt awareness programs including lectures and colloquies provided by professional academics.

2. The government has to determine some strategies that assist in Integrating the awareness culture of the school with that of the university; when a student gets a good awareness in their schools and finds that in their universities, there will be a bit space opportunity allowed to time waste or wrongful use of social networks.
3. Students' families have a significant role in monitoring and controlling the use of social media through proper orientation of the family members.
4. Students themselves are to organize their educational activities so that they can activate their social media in favor of their educational goals.
5. The Government also has a significant role by determining restrictions and firewalls on some saucy electronic sites that may harm the society culture.
6. The government is to cooperate with universities, private and public, to reinforce the social ethics and respect of its culture.

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